

TO CONDUCT A PATHOGENETIC AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF TUBERCULOSIS OF PERIPHERAL LYMPH NODES.

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Introduction. Peripheral lymph node tuberculosis (PLNTB) is the most common form of extra-pulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB) in people with and without HIV. The cervical region is the most frequently affected location. Mycobacterium tuberculosis is the most common offender. Impacts are more likely to affect female young people who are economically productive. Tubercular lymphadenitis is mostly a medical condition, even though frequent removal of the affected node may be required to avoid scarring. However, surgical excision is associated with a somewhat worse prognosis than medical treatment alone [1,2,3]. Nevertheless, many of these people develop sinuses, enlarge pre-existing lesions, or develop new lymph nodes or illnesses in spite of medical treatment. Treating cervical lymph node tuberculosis (CLNTB), a cosmo-sensitive area, makes this more challenging. This review's primary goal is to provide a succinct appraisal of the value of enhancing treatment strategies for peripheral lymph node tuberculosis with the use of credible scientific studies [4,5,6].

Material and methods of treatment. Throughout the course of treating lymph node TB, the patient and the doctor must coordinate. The duration of the treatment depends on the patient's level of persistence. Patients with active therapy for lymph node tuberculosis can lower their chance of developing sequelae of tuberculosis. Currently, lymph node TB is treated using the following methods: Internal medicine: Patients have to follow their doctor's instructions. The most crucial thing is to take the drug exactly as directed, at the right time, and without stopping in the middle. The duration of internal medicine treatment for lymph node TB is around eight months. Attack treatment lasts for about three months, after which there is maintenance. A paradoxical reaction (PR) happens when pre-existing disease worsens or new lesions emerge in a patient who has been receiving anti-tuberculosis (TB) treatment for at least two weeks, unless there has been a recorded relapse or the patient has another illness. The majority of PR cases in individuals with peripheral LNTB manifest as enlarged LNs, new affected nodes, pain, and sinus discharge between three weeks and four months after beginning anti-TB medication. This situation highlights the importance of distinguishing between adverse drug reactions, new infections, drug resistance, and poor patient compliance. Additionally, compared to less than 5% of pulmonary TB cases in HIV-negative individuals, a PR occurs very frequently—roughly 20% of patients with peripheral LNTB after anti-TB treatment.

Result and discussion. Extrapulmonary tuberculosis (EPTB), an infectious disease that affects organs other than the lungs, is caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB). In 2021, EPTB was responsible for 17% of the 6.4 million cases that were reported; this number ranged from 8% in the Western Pacific Region to 23% in the Eastern Mediterranean Region. Lymph node tuberculosis (LNTB) is one of the most common presentations of EPTB, accounting for 20 to 40 percent of all cases. The majority of earlier studies on LNTB focused on peripheral LNTB rather than mediastinal LNTB because peripheral lymph nodes (LNs) are easier to locate and access. This retrospective observational investigation looked at the clinical course of mediastinal LNTB, the prevalence of PR in patients with mediastinal LNTB, and risk factors associated with PR. At a median of 4.4 months after beginning anti-TB medication, 21 (17%) of the 125 patients in our experiment obtained PR. Using multivariable logistic regression analysis, PR was found to be independently associated with younger age, larger LN, and lymphocytopenia. This is the first study that, as far as we know, describes the clinical course of mediastinal LNTB and the characteristics of PR in this illness.

Conclusion. This report presents the clinical, radiologic, and pathologic outcomes of a six-month course of treatment for tuberculous lymphadenitis. The limitations of the study are as follows: Not all patients with residual LNs had FNAB, and some specimens were inappropriate. CT scans were not obtained throughout the following follow-up period, and most patients with residual LNs were on antituberculous treatment for more than six months. Finding the variables linked to TB recurrence in the remaining LN group is the next stage. More follow-up studies with a bigger patient group are needed to achieve statistical significance.

After six months of antituberculous treatment, the existence of residual LNs in individuals with CTBL does not always indicate recurrence or treatment failure, even though radiologic and pathologic characteristics are consistent with TB. Younger people may still have residual LNs after six months of treatment, and reevaluation may be necessary after a brief period of observation. The long treatment duration that has been commonly observed in patients with residual LNs should be reexamined, since this study suggests that a six-month antituberculous therapy may be sufficient.

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